

MASTERING TEACHING ENGLISH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation: In this paperwork is described methods in teaching and developing language skills. Such as listening skill, speaking, skill, reading skill and writing skill.

Key words: Mastering teaching, media, method technic, improving, skill .

Language has some skills to understand; listening skill, speaking skill, reading skill, and writing skill. Those skills have their own characteristics to be understood and to be mastered. Mastering all those skills needs some certain method too, but we can learn them as step by step. Every language teacher should understand well related to the skills when they are teaching language. It influences teaching the language. As a teacher should understand well which skill the students should learn first, how to teach each skill, and what the characters of the language learners. When the teacher understand those well, it will be easy to recognize the learners, to choose the suitable method, and to find the suitable materials. Teaching foreign language is different from teaching first language, even though some of the orders are same. Before we teach second language, of course we have to understand the first language then before we learn foreign language we have to understand the second language. Even sometimes we do not understand each of them well, but it should be better if we understand well. Those can help the

learners easier to acquire the second language or foreign language. It is because the language can be used as a tool to explain and study second language and also foreign language. When the language learners learner the language they must find some difficult word or phrases, they can understand the meaning from their own language explanation or definition. Sometimes, different language has different definition and term, out of the context. Related to teaching language, because language has some skills, teaching language also has some certain method to teach. And teaching language need much practice too to master the language. If the learners learn the theory of linguistics, they do not need to much practice the language, for example they do not need much to practice speaking and writing in a context. They just learn the theory of linguistics. Moreover, if the learners learn the language to teach it into Young Learners, they have to try to practice it actively, well, and fluently. It is because young learners are active learners need to be taught actively too. And usually the young learners emphasize on language practice. They need the language to be practiced and used. Most of them use the language orally. In Indonesia, now English is out of curriculum for elementary school, even though at the previous period about 2010s Indonesian curriculum placed English Language inside. In Indonesia since 1994, elementary school have been taught English as a local content subject. According to Kunjana Rahardi, a master of socio-Linguistic Gajah Mada University (UGM), teaching English in early age will impact bad effect for the children related to the national language (Indonesia). Mastering mother language and national language will influence second or foreign language acquisition (voaindonesia, 2012). Whereas, some schools places the English into extra classes or additional classes, some schools do not leave English as a compulsory subject, but in some countries English is a compulsory subject in the early primary grades (Niclove,2009;pinter 2006). Moreover, Shin and Crandall

(2011) showed that for recently years, about 50 countries in the world placed English Language as a compulsory subject at the third grade. Many foreign languages are offered by some schools but English becomes first choices. The parents believes that English is the first foreign language in Indonesia and by English their children can develop and explore their knowledge well, then their children can be easier to go abroad to reach their dream to be success and famous people. Many people want their children master the English since young or child. They ask because of the high demand of English Teaching young learners are different from teaching older learners. Young learners have their own characteristics. Older learners have their intention to learn and study but young learners are not. Young learners just follow what they want and like. They do not really respect to other people. They like to enjoy their own life and style. Because of that, we need to understand their characteristics related to Teaching English for Young Learners. Young Learners Young learners are different from old learners of course. They are unique; they have smart brain which is fresh, clean, and fast. Most of them are attractive. Who is young learner? There are some opinions related to them. The British Philosopher, John Stuart Mill started to learn Greek at three years old, but it was not generally children. Some of them said that young learners are children whose age less than 12 years old. According to Scooth and Lisbeth, young learners are they who have age under 11 years old. For the teacher who concern in teaching English to young learners they have to understand the characteristics of young learners in order understanding the students' needs, knowing the suitable method to teaching young learners. According to Scooth and Lisbeth (1992) in Handoyo, there are some characteristics of young learners: Children age 8-10 are mature enough. They have particular point of view . They can describe the difference between fact and fiction. They are curious of asking

questions. They believe of what is said and the “real” word to express and comprehend meaning/message. Based on those characteristics, we cannot say that children do not have any world, do not understand the old people, do not understand the environment. They are really can feel the environment around them and they can say truth based on what they see and understand. According Wendy and Lisbeth (1992), they divided the children into two levels, first; five to seven years old, second; eight to ten years old. They divide the pupils become two based on the experience of acquiring the language. The first level, they usually get not more foreign language experience, the second level, they who have more foreign language experience. It means that both level sometimes have same age and those are not to much because of the age but because of they foreign language experiences. So, it is possible for the pupils of seven years old are into second level. In our country and culture we can divide the pupil based on the class they study if they study in formal school, but if the class is in informal school we can divide the pupils based on their foreign experiences or foreign language ability. Teaching English for Young Learners In a teaching context, teaching children foreign language are different from teaching mother language, but potentially, their acquiring and learning foreign language, and even they learn more quickly than they learn after puberty (McLaughlin,1978). In other hand, Long (1990) stated that children are less capable of absorbing or acquiring foreign language. There are two kinds of classes in our country, formal school and informal school. Wherever the place of the young learner class is, they are young learners who learn foreign language. The teacher should understand and master in teaching young learners. An English teacher for young learners should be master of the English itself, the methods and models of teaching English, especially for young learners. An English teacher also must be able to be creative teacher, they can make and use many

things become the requirement of teaching young learners which are suitable of it. For additions, as a teacher should teach using heard so the teacher can connect between what the teacher feels and wants to reach to the children. If the teacher can feel what the students' feel or connect their feeling to learn, the teacher will be easy to teach and the students will be easy to understand what the teacher delivered. When the teacher just what to teach and to deliver the material in not enough, it can be less of useful. English is not main subject for the children to learn. It is just additional; moreover it is just a foreign

language. For the children it can be difficult, it can be easy based on their experience of foreign language. The children do not understand what for the English is. But as a teacher, we have to make the children like the English then the English can be accepted by them. Related to the characteristics of the young learners, what should we prepare for teaching English to young learners? o the teacher should be attractive and careful to the children o the teacher should always be happy and cheerful o the method and the media should be interesting o it is a must to include song and game o the teacher should refresh always every time they feel bored Children are mostly attractive, happy, and cheerful; so the teacher should be a bit like the children; cheerful, happy, and attractive. The teacher feels what the children feel, the children need to be cared and got more attention. If the teacher just teach the material, of course the children feel little lazy. It is because, children do not know the order of learning, they do not know the need of learning, and they just want to enjoy their life. Teacher should be happy and cheerful too because, the children will not feel enjoy the class if the teacher does not feel happy and enjoy the class. Another preparation to teach English is method and media. The teacher should use interesting media and method; like song, colorful card, games. Those are suitable for the children. Children like colorful thing, games, and

happy song. It does not mean that every meeting game and song include in teaching and learning process. It is just used in some of the whole meeting. There are some technics of teaching young learners according Suyatno (2007), o listen and repeat o listen and do o song and game o group discussion English is foreign language which is different from children first language. It has different voice from “bahasa Indonesia”, so listening and repeating is suitable for the beginners, young learner is the beginner. They like to follow the teacher, repeat what the teacher said and repeat what they listen. The children can do after they listen and understand. Songs in teaching English for Young learners Song is some words and rhyme which is delivered in rhythm and beautiful tone. The teacher uses song to teach to make students interested in learning English, if they are interested in, they will be easy to learn and enjoy the class. Song is created to be enjoyed and not only be enjoyed but also to propose teaching and learning process. Teacher can use song to teach vocabularies, phrases, sentences rule, or others. So the teacher can decide the suitable song for the teaching and learning needs and purposes. So the children can enjoy the song while learning some materials, sometimes they do not realize that they are learning during singing a song. There are some characteristic of songs for children:

1. The notes of the song should be the easy to follow
2. There are many repetitions, usually to memorize some vocabularies or phrases.
3. Interesting, happy, fast and attractive
4. The song is usually short

Teaching English for young Learners is interesting activities. Before teaching young learners, teacher should know the characteristics of young learners and the student’s needs. Then the teacher can divide the method, the model or technic of

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teaching young learners. Teaching Young Learners should be interesting, happy, and attractive. The teacher can use colorful picture, song, and game. Those should be suitable for the children. Then every teacher of young learners must be creative and always cheerful, because he/she face children. Every kinds of media, method, and technic can be improved by the teacher as creative as possible.